

STIFFNESS AND STRENGTH OF MISORIENTED WHISKER-TOUGHENING CERAMICS WITH RESIDUAL THERMO-STRAIN

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ABSTRACT

The stiffness and Strength of whisker-toughening Ceramics with randomly distributed microcracks are estimated by means of equivalent inclusion method and mean field theory. Some important factor, including the residual thermo-strain, the misorientation of whiskers and microcracks, the aspect and the fraction of whiskers, the length and the fraction of microcracks, are considered quantitatively and their influence on the Stiffness and Strength researched. The calculated results are discussed and some significant conclusions are obtained.

1. INTRODUCTION

Whisker-toughening ceramics is a kind of inhomogeneous material and is processed at high temperature. Therefore, the residual thermo-strain exists during cooling. Meanwhile, microcracks will be induced at some weak position due to the residual thermo-stress and external load. Generally a large number of microcracks exist in matrix and at matrix/whisker interface and are benefit for the toughening of ceramics, although the toughening is reduced. In matrix, the microcracks and whiskers are distributed randomly and affect the behaviors of composites greatly. Otherwise, the thermo-strain, the fraction and aspect of whiskers, the fractions and length of microcracks are also important factors to be considered. It, however, is difficult to consider all these factors synthetically. Theoretical and experimental research on whisker/ceramics composite has been done and some new theoretical models have been proposed, but they are not universal. Takao et al^[1] estimated the longitudinal effective stiffness of composite with misoriented short fibers using equivalent inclusion method. Taya et al^[2] calculated the stress induced by thermo-strain in two dimensional misoriented short-fibers composite and the result shown that fiber fraction affects the stress more greatly than fiber distribution. Taya and Mura^[3] proposed that microcracks exist at the fibers' top in unidirectional short fiber composite material and

estimated the stiffness and strength, but the interaction between microcracks was not considered. Taya et al^[4] still calculated the stiffness and strength of aligned short fiber composite with aligned microcracks. In the above works, many important factors were not considered, such as thermo-strain, the misorientation of whiskers and microcracks and their interaction. In this paper, a new model is proposed to consider the influence of all these factors quantitatively. By equivalent inclusion method and mean field theory, the stress, stiffness and strength of whisker-toughening ceramics are calculated. The results suggest that the present model is effective and practical in research of whisker-toughening ceramics. Some important conclusions are obtained.

2. STRESS FIELD

Figure.1 is the material element in which microcracks and whiskers are distributed randomly. The whiskers are viewed as long prolate spheroids and the microcracks, as penny shape voids (Figure.3). Suppose that all of the particles are of the same shape and the

Figure 1 The element of materials

Figure 2 Transformation of coordinate system

Figure 3 The orientation: (a) particle (b) microcrack

microcracks are, too. The transformation between the local and global coordinate system is

$$\mathbf{X}^1 - T_1 \mathbf{X}, \quad \mathbf{X}^2 - T_2 \mathbf{X} \quad (1)$$

where T_1 and T_2 are the transformation matrixes of whiskers and microcracks respectively and can be written as follow,

$$T_1 = \begin{vmatrix} \cos\alpha\cos\beta & \sin\alpha\sin\beta & \cos\beta \\ -\sin\alpha & \cos\alpha & 0 \\ -\cos\alpha\cos\beta & -\sin\alpha\sin\beta & \sin\beta \end{vmatrix} \quad (2)$$

T_2 is the same as T_1 in form except β to be replaced with θ and φ . Under an external load σ° and a residual thermo-strain ϵ^T , there is an average interaction strain ϵ between the whiskers and microcracks. The average stress in matrix is

$$\sigma_m = \sigma^\circ + C \epsilon \quad (3)$$

By the equivalent inclusion method^[5], the stress of a whisker in the global coordinate system is

$$\sigma' = C_1 (\epsilon^\circ + \epsilon + T_1' S_1 T_1 \epsilon^{**} - \epsilon^T) - C [\epsilon^\circ + \epsilon + (T_1' S_1 T_1 - I) \epsilon^{**}] \quad (4)$$

where C and C_1 are the moduli of matrix and whiskers. ϵ° satisfies $\sigma^\circ = C \epsilon^\circ$. $\epsilon^{**} = \epsilon^* + \epsilon^T$ and ϵ^* is the equivalent strain. S_1 is the Eshelby tensor of a whisker. The equivalent relation of a microcrack in the global coordinate system is

$$\sigma^2 = C [\epsilon^\circ + \epsilon + (T_2' S_2 T_2 - I) \epsilon^{2*}] \quad (5)$$

where S_2 and ϵ^{2*} are the Eshelby tensor and the equivalent strain of a microcrack. From Equation(4) and Equation(5), ϵ^{**} and ϵ^{2*} are solved.

$$\epsilon^{**} = (\Delta C T_1' S_1 T_1 + C)^{-1} [-\Delta C (\epsilon^\circ + \epsilon) + C_1 \epsilon] \quad (6)$$

$$\epsilon^{2*} = -(T_2' S_2 T_2 - I)^{-1} (\epsilon^\circ + \epsilon) \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta C = C_1 - C$. I is the identity tensor. Because the interaction stress is equilibrated by itself, namely,

$$\int_V \sigma^i dV = 0$$

$$\int_{V-V_1-V_2} C\tilde{\varepsilon} dV + \int_{V_1} C[\tilde{\varepsilon} + (T_1' S_1 T_1 - I) \varepsilon^{**}] dV + \int_{V_2} C[\tilde{\varepsilon} + (T_2' S_2 T_2 - I) \varepsilon^{2*}] dV = 0 \quad (8)$$

where V , V_1 and V_2 are the volumes of material element, whiskers and microcracks. The orientation distributing functions of the whiskers and microcracks are $g_1(\alpha, \beta)$ and $g_2(\theta, \varphi)$ respectively. $\alpha \in [\alpha_1, \alpha_2]$, $\beta \in [\beta_1, \beta_2]$, $\theta \in [\theta_1, \theta_2]$, $\varphi \in [\varphi_1, \varphi_2]$, α_i, β_i , and θ_i, φ_i are the orientation scopes. The fractions of whiskers and microcracks f_1 and f_2 yield,

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_1} dV = \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_1} \Omega_1 g_1(\alpha, \beta) \sin\beta d\alpha d\beta \quad (9)$$

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_2} dV = \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_2} \Omega_2 g_2(\theta, \varphi) \sin\varphi d\theta d\varphi \quad (10)$$

where Ω_1 is the volume of a single whisker and Ω_2 , the volume of a microcrack. If

$$a_1 = \int_{\beta_1}^{\beta_2} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} g_1(\alpha, \beta) \sin\beta d\alpha d\beta \quad (11)$$

$$a_2 = \int_{\varphi_1}^{\varphi_2} \int_{\theta_1}^{\theta_2} g_2(\theta, \varphi) \sin\varphi d\theta d\varphi \quad (12)$$

substitute Equation(9)-(12) into Equation(8), $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ is solved,

$$\tilde{\varepsilon} = [(1-f_2)I - \frac{f_1}{a_1} R \Delta C]^{-1} [(\frac{f_1}{a_1} R \Delta C - f_2 I) C^{-1} \sigma^0 - \frac{f_1}{a_1} R C_1 \varepsilon^T] \quad (13)$$

$$R = \int_{\beta_1}^{\beta_2} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} (T_1' S_1 T_1 - I) (\Delta C T_1' S_1 T_1 + C)^{-1} g_1(\alpha, \beta) \sin\beta d\alpha d\beta \quad (14)$$

The stress σ_1 in a whisker is given by

$$\sigma' = \sigma^0 + C\tilde{\varepsilon} + C(T_1' S_1 T_1 - I) (\Delta C T_1' S_1 T_1 + C)^{-1} [-\Delta C(C^{-1} \sigma^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}) + C_1 \varepsilon^T] \quad (15)$$

Equation(3),(13) and (15) imply that the stress in composite doesn't depend on the distribution of microcracks. When $f_2 \ll 1$, the influence of microcracks vanishes.

3. FAILURE CRITERION AND EFFECTIVE CONSTITUTIVE RELATION

Let n represent the number of microcracks in unit volume, a_c , the radius of a microcrack and t , the crack opening length of a microcrack $t/a_c < 1\%$ and can be neglected during calculation. The Gibbs free energy can be written as^[6]: Equation(16). combining

$$\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^0 \varepsilon^0 + \frac{1}{2V} \int_{V_1} (\sigma^0 \varepsilon^{**} + \sigma^{-1} \varepsilon^T) dV + \frac{1}{2V} \int_{V_2} \sigma^0 \varepsilon^T dV \quad (16)$$

Equation(6)-(12) and through the formula $\Omega_2=4/3\pi a^2t$,Equation(16) is changed into

$$\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^{\circ} C^{-1} \sigma^{\circ} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{f_1}{a_1} \int_{\beta_1}^{\beta_2} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} (\sigma^{\circ} \varepsilon^{**} + \sigma^{-1} \varepsilon^T) g_1(\alpha, \beta) \sin \beta d\alpha d\beta - \frac{2\pi n a^2}{3 a_2} \sigma^{\circ} Q (C^{-1} \sigma^{\circ} + \xi) \quad (17)$$

and

$$Q = \int_{\varphi_1}^{\varphi_2} \int_{\theta_1}^{\theta_2} T_2' T_0 T_2 g_2(\theta, \varphi) \sin \varphi d\theta d\varphi \quad (18)$$

where T_0 is a six dimensional second-order tensor, and

$$T_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\mu}{1-\mu} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\mu}{1-\mu} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\mu}{1-\mu} \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

S_1 and S_2 are symmetry fourth-order tensor and can be changed into a six dimensional second-order tensor so as to be calculated more easily^[6]. Therefore, T_1 and T_2 should be also changed from three to six dimensional tensor^[6].

If the released energy to form the unit area of cracks is G_c , the total energy released rate G^P is

$$G^P = \pi a^2 G_c \dot{n} + 2\pi a n G_c \dot{a} \quad (20)$$

In Equation(20), the first term represents the energy release rate of new crack and the second term, the one of the original cracks' expansion. The released part of Gibbs free energy is as follows.

$$\dot{\psi}_c = F^n + F^a \dot{a} \quad (21)$$

when $G^p = \dot{\varphi}_c$, the energy release equation is obtained.

$$(F^n - \pi a^2 G_c) dn = (2\pi a G_c - F^n) da \quad (22)$$

Combining Equation(20) and (21), Equation(22) is turned into

$$a (ah - \frac{3}{2} \pi G_c) dn = 3n (\pi G_c - ah) da \quad (23)$$

If σ^0 satisfies $ah < \pi G_c$, the left term in Equation(23) ≤ 0 and the right term ≥ 0 . Therefore, Equation(23) is feasible only if $dn = da = 0$, namely, the density and length of microcracks doesn't increase. When $ah = \pi G_c$, Equation(23) requires $dn = 0$ and da is an arbitrary number, which suggests that microcracks expand firstly $ah = \pi G_c$ represent a critical failure condition of the composite.

$$\sigma^0 Q(C^{-1}\sigma^0 + \xi) = \frac{\pi(1-2\mu)(2-\mu)a_2}{8(1-\mu)a} G_c \quad (24)$$

when $ah \leq \pi G_c$, the composite material is elastic. Through the intrinsic theory and Equation(13),(15), the elastic constitutive relation is described as

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \sigma^0} = C^{-1}\sigma^0 + \frac{f_1}{a_1} P [C_1 \epsilon^T - \Delta C (\xi + C^{-1}\sigma^0)] + \frac{32(1-\mu)n a^3}{3(1-2\mu)(2-\mu)a_2} Q(C^{-1}\sigma^0 + \xi) + f_1 \epsilon^T \quad (25)$$

By Equation(25), the stiffness of the composite material can be calculated.

4. THEORETICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An example is calculated that the whiskers of Al_2O_3 and microcracks yield uniformly random distribution in xoy plane of SiC matrix. Therefore the distribution scope is $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ and $\varphi = \beta = \pi/2$. The thermo-strain ϵ^T is replaced by ΔT (temperature reduction) through the relation: $\epsilon^T = (\alpha_w - \alpha_m) \Delta T$. α_w and α_m are the thermo-expansion coefficient of whiskers and matrix. The properties of Al_2O_3 and SiC are illustrated in Table.1. E and μ are elastic modulus and Poisson ratio b/a is the aspect of a whisker.

Table 1. The properties of the components in SiC/ Al_2O_3 w

Components	E(GPa)	μ	$\alpha(10^{-5})$	b/a	$G_c(J/M^2)$
SiC	650	0.12	5	-	40
Al_2O_3	450	0.19	9	20:1	-

Under unidirectional tension along x axis, the stiffness E_c and the strength σ_u of SiC/Al₂O₃w material are calculated through Equation(24) and (25) respectively. The results are shown in Figure 4-8. In view of Figure 4, the increment of whiskers' content causes the reduction of the strength slightly and the thermo-strain strengthens the reduction, which is implied in Figure.6. Figure.5 shows the trend in the strength σ_u with the microcracks, involving their content f_2 and length a_c . σ_u isn't almost affected by f_2 and decreases rapidly with the increment of the length a_c . The aspect b/a of whiskers is a important factor affecting the strength when $b/a < 25$, but it doesn't influence the strength when $b/a > 25$. It is possible that increment of b/a reduces the load tolerance of whiskers and the stress in whiskers is transferred into matrix. Therefore the stress concentration at the microcracks' tips is increased. Figure.7 and Figure.8 show the effective modulus of SiC/Al₂O₃w material. The increment of the whiskers' content reduces the effective modulus, but b/a influences the modulus quite slightly (Figure.7). The thermo-strain makes a notable impact to the modulus and is the most important factor affecting effective modulus. The relation between ΔT and E_c is almost linear and thermo-strain causes the reduction of effective modulus. In a word, the present results and discussion suggest that the stress in whiskers isn't influenced by the distribution of microcracks and is the function of the content of microcracks. The main factor affecting strength are the length of microcracks, the residual thermo-strain the properties of the components in composite. Meanwhile, the thermo-strain and the properties of the components are also the main factor influencing the effective modulus of the composite and the content of microcracks is the most important factor. In general, then microcracks and residual thermo-strain have to be considered in research of the behaviors of whisker-toughening ceramics.

Figure 4 Relation between strength and the content of whiskers.

Figure 5 Influence of microcracks: content f_2 (when $a_0=0.7\mu\text{m}$), length(when $f_2=0.2\%$)

Figure 6 Trends in strength with the thermo-strain and the aspect of whiskers

Figure 7 Trends in effective modulus with the content and aspect b/a of whiskers

Figure 8 Trends in effective modulus with thermo-strain and the content of microcracks

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